

In(Probability) Carrying the Information of a Conserved Quantity and Eigenvalue Equations

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In information theory, $\ln(\text{Probability})$ is called information. We argue that in various physical problems this information is linked with a conserved quantity and a variable which changes. For example, in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case the conserved quantity is $1/\text{Temperature}$ and the variable $e+V(x) = \text{energy}$. For a quantum free particle, the conserved quantity is momentum and the variable x . "e" may change subject to the conserved quantity $1/T$ and x may change subject to the conserved quantity p . Given that probability may be unnormalized, changes may be expressed in relative terms i.e. in terms of a derivative of $\ln(P)$ i.e. information. We argue that the derivative of $\ln(P)$ with respect to the variable which changes yields the value of the conserved quantity in special cases for which the conserved quantity is the only information governing changes in the probability distribution. Thus one has an eigenvalue equation: $d/\text{variable} \ln(P) = \text{conserved quantity}$. This implies that $\ln(P) = \text{variable} * \text{conserved quantity}$. This may lead to two different kinds of conservation equations. In the MB case, e is the variable and $1/T$ the conserved quantity, but $\ln(P(e_1)) + \ln(P(e_2)) = 1/T (e_1+e_2) = \ln(P(e_1+e_2))$. An eigenvalue equation allows for this conservation. In the quantum free particle case: $\ln(P(k_1,x)) + \ln(P(k_2,x))$ where $P = \text{wavefunction} = \exp(ipx)$ (i.e. the square-root type probability is used), one has $k_1+k_2=k_3$ with x the variable canceling out. (In the MB case, it was $1/T$ the conserved quantity canceling). Again, the eigenvalue equation allows for this conservation, this time of the conserved quantity.

We note that the eigenvalue equation is a special case and not only probability distributions are associated with it. For example, a power law distribution's changes in its variable do not depend only on the conserved quantity $1/T$ in $P(e/T) = \text{power law}$.

In(Probability)

In information theory, $\ln(\text{Probability})$ is called information. One may also note that it appears in Stirling's high N approximation: $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$ of the \ln of the number of arrangements of a quantity (say energy E) among N particles with each arrangement carrying the same weight i.e.

$$\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!) \approx N \ln(N) - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((1))$$

Thus taking $d/dn(e_i)$ yields $\ln(n(e_i))$, the information of information theory. {As an aside, taking $d/dn(e_i)$ is equivalent to extremizing $n \ln(N)$, but usually a constraint is needed. If the constraint is of the form: $eP(e)$ i.e. the average value of the variable, then $\ln(P(e_i/T))$ and e_i/T become equivalent. }

We argue that $\ln(\text{Probability})$ serves another role. Probabilities are usually normalized and in such a case, a derivative of a probability has meaning. If a probability is not normalized, however, a derivative of a probability has no meaning. It needs to be considered relative to

something, such as the probability itself. $\ln(P(y))$ serves the purpose of ensuring a meaningful derivative i.e.

$$d/dy \ln(P(y)) = dP/dy / P \quad ((2))$$

Thus, as argued in previous notes, we expect to see $\ln(P)$ appear in equations used to derive probabilities (or densities) because these usually yield an unnormalized probability function.

The Argument of a Probability Distribution

For a given probability distribution, P is a function of a variable which may change i.e. $P(y)$. Probability has not units, but y has units so it seems:

$$P(y/b) \text{ where } b \text{ is a constant which has the same units as } y. \quad ((3))$$

If b is a constant, however, then it is conserved. Thus we argue that the arguments of a probability distribution should contain y/b . As a result, one expects not only $\ln(P)$, but $\ln(P(y/b))$ in an equation used to derive a probability distribution.

Conservation and an Eigenvalue Equation

We argued above that a probability distribution should be written in terms of $P(y/b)$ where y is variable and $1/b$ a constant with the same units. As a result, $1/b$ is a conserved quantity. Given that $\ln(P)$ is information in information theory and that y may change it seems natural to consider:

$$d \ln(P(y/b)) / dy \quad ((4)) \text{ as a quantity of interest.}$$

If the conserved quantity is the driver of changes in y , one might suggest an eigenvalue equation i.e.

$$d \ln(P(y/b)) / dy = +/- 1/b \quad ((4)) \text{ Here } d/dy \text{ is the generator of translations in } y \text{ space.}$$

Does ((4)) appear in any physical theories? We argue that it is present for a Maxwell-Boltzmann situation for which the unnormalized probability is: $P(e) = \exp(-e/T)$. In fact, ((4)) is equivalent to the Zwanzig form of the Fokker-Planck equation (1) for $D=\text{constant}$ and $g=\text{constant}$ and $dP/dt \text{ partial} = 0$ i.e.

$$dP/dt \text{ partial} = 0 = -p/m dP/dx \text{ partial} + d/dp \{ dV/dx + g p \} P + d/dp D dP/dp \quad ((5))$$

where $e=pp/2m + V(x)$ and d/dp is the partial derivative with respect to momentum.

$$((5)) \text{ becomes: } gP + D/m dP/de = 0 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is an eigenvalue equation of the form of ((4)).

Another example comes from the quantum mechanics of a free particle. In such a case, the wavefunction (or unnormalized square root probability) is $\exp(ipx)$. This also satisfies an eigenvalue equation of the form of ((4)) with +/- replaced with +/- i because one has a two dimensional dynamic probability which must indicate the direction of motion.

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

In this case, p is the conserved quantity and it is of the form $1/L$ where L is the wavelength so that it cancels the units of x. We use $\hbar=1$.

Eigenvalue Equation and a Loss of “Information”

The eigenvalue equation ((4)) is a “special” equation and it carries with it certain consequences. ((4)) does not hold in all probabilistic cases and is shown in the next section. One important consequence of ((4)) is the notion of conservation which may be applied either to the running variable y or the conserved quantity $1/b$.

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which $1/\text{Temperature}$ is constant, one has:

$$P(e_1/T) P(e_2/T) = P((e_1+e_2)/T) \quad ((8))$$

The idea is that $\frac{d}{de} \ln(P(e_i/T)) = -1/T$ i.e. only “information” about the conserved quantity is obtained. There is no extra “functional” information obtained by taking the derivative. Thus taking \ln of ((8)) yields:

$\ln(e_1/T) + \ln(e_2/T) = \ln(P((e_1+e_2)/T))$ which cannot carry more information than:

$$e_1/T + e_2/T = (e_1+e_2)/T.$$

In the quantum free particle case, it is the conserved quantity k which is part of an equation of the nature of ((8)) i.e.

$$\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2) x) \quad ((9))$$

In both ((8)) and ((9)) there is a loss of information in the sense that any e_1 and e_2 in ((8)) which have the sum $e_1+e_2=E$ have the same product probability. This is why for a fixed E any arrangement has the same weight. In the quantum case, any p_1 and p_2 which add to an overall p have the same product probability.

Non-Eigenvalue Equation for Probability

In the above sections we argued that $\ln(P)$ should appear in an equation used to derive probability and that it should have an argument y/b where b is a constant or conserved quantity.

That does not mean that the eigenvalue equation ((4)) is the only scenario possible. For example, the power law distribution:

$$P(e/T) \text{ unnormalized} = (1-ke/T)^{1/k} \quad (k=\text{constant}) \quad ((10))$$

is a solution of the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck equation ((5)) for $g=\text{constant}$ and $D=gmb(1-ke/b)$. In such a case: $d/de \ln(P)$ does not equal the conserved quantity $1/b$, but rather:

$$d/de \ln(P(e/T)) = -1/ \{mb(1-ke/b)\} \quad ((11))$$

In other words, there is more “information” in the derivative of $\ln(P)$ than just the conserved quantity. As a result:

$$P(e_1/T)P(e_2/T) \text{ not} = P((e_1+e_2)/T) \quad ((12))$$

P is a function of e_1/T and so one has the equation:

$$\ln(P(e_1/T)) + \ln(P(e_2/T)) = \ln(P(e_3/T))$$

, but this is a conservation equation, namely $\ln(1-ke_1/T) + \ln(1-ke_2/T) = \ln(1-ke_3/T)$ which is independent of a conservation of energy statement $e_1+e_2=e_3$. Thus there is more “information” in the power law scenario we argue. It does not simply consider all distributions of energy as having equal probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that information from information theory $\ln(P(y))$ also serves the purpose of ensuring that a derivative $d/dy \ln(P) = dP/dy / P$ is a relative probability derivative because for an unnormalized probability distribution, dP/dy does not have meaning as it has no units. Thus we expect to see $\ln(P)$ in an equation used to derive the probability distribution. Furthermore, due to the lack of units, one expects $P(y/b)$ where y is a variable and $1/b$ a constant with the same units. This suggests $1/b$ is a conserved quantity. We argue that it is possible to create a “special” equation for a system in which the conserved quantity governs the changes in the variable i.e. $d/dy P(y/b) = +/- 1/b P(y/b)$. This is an eigenvalue equation and it appears in the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution case. In fact, it is the eigenvalue equation which “falls out” of the Zwanzig Fokker-Planck equation for $g=\text{constant}$, $D=\text{constant}$ (see ((5))). In addition, we argue that a very similar eigenvalue equation applies to the quantum free particle i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This special scenario comes with the extra condition that $P(e_1/T)P(e_2/T) = P((e_1+e_2)/T)$ or in the quantum case: $P(p_1x)P(p_2x) = P((p_1+p_2)x)$ where $P=\exp(ipx)$ in this case (i.e. a square root probability). In other words, the product probability relationship is identical to the conservation of the arguments. This property does not hold in all probabilistic situations. In particular, the power law distribution $C(1-ke/T)^{1/k}$ has the property: $d/de P(e/T) = \text{constant}/(1-ke/T)$. Thus there is more information in this situation and an eigenvalue equation does not

apply. Changes in $P(e/T)$ (due to a change in the variable) are not simply governed by the conserved quantity.

References

1. Ran, G. and Du, J. Are power law distributions an equilibrium distribution or a stationary nonequilibrium distribution? (2013 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1403.5441.pdf>